

Classification of movement patterns of subviral particles using a support vector machine

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Abstract: This work deals with the classification of subviral particle movement. Preparatory, tracks were humanly assigned into classes. Coordinates, obtained by a subviral particle tracker and metadata were used to determine parameters that quantify movement patterns in space and time. The information content of the parameters was condensed by principal component analysis. A scatter plot of the components including the manual mapping shows a clear separation of the tracks and confirms the hypothesis. Using this, an algorithm was developed to classify new tracks automatically. Data classification was performed by a support vector machine trained on detected and human-assigned subviral particle tracks.

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I. Introduction

With increasing globalization, the risk of pandemic outbreaks is growing, as the current Corona pandemic distinctly demonstrates. The Ebola virus, as a pathogen of hemorrhagic fever with a mortality rate of around 50%, is still a research subject for virologists all over the world [1]. This makes it all the more important to gain new insights into the pathogen, which can serve as a basis for the development of new medication. A fundamental aspect for this could be the movement behavior of subviral particles, especially if it changes after the addition of pharmaceuticals, within the host cell. The cells analyzed for this work were infected with the Marburg virus, whose properties are similar compared to those of the Ebola virus. For this purpose, fluorescence image sequences were provided by scientists from the Institute of Virology at the Philipps-University of Marburg, which originate from an innovative fluorescence live cell imaging method to visualize intracellular processes [2]. Algorithms to automatically track subviral particles from fluorescence images were introduced by Kienzle et al. [3] and further developed by Rausch et al. [4].

The work "Automated Classification of Directed and Undirected Movement of Subviral Particles" by Kaak et al. [5] serves as a basis. The division of motion patterns into

three classes is suggested. Particles with a directed, moderate or chaotic movement pattern (Fig. 1) are to be distinguished. The aim of this work is to find suitable parameters and to automatically assign the tracks of subviral particles to the corresponding class.

II. Material and methods

In advance, 33 track traces were visually assessed by a virologist from the Institute of Virology at the Philipps-University of Marburg and manually assigned to the respective class. These tracks and their assignments serve as training data for the presented algorithm. To quantify the motion patterns, 9 parameters were used, which were calculated using the tracking coordinates and the metadata. The parameters fractal dimension [6], straightness (ratio of displacement and length), curvature [7] and the results of the contrast function from the mean square deviation [5] refer to the spatial extent of the track. In addition, the acceleration and velocity describe the properties of the particle motion and consider not only the space but also the dimension of time. For this purpose, the averaged velocity and the averaged acceleration were calculated over one track each. The acceleration is considered twice: As absolute and as non-absolute value to include negative acceleration. The particles' velocity is additionally calculated using a sliding window of size 2 and 10.

Figure 1: Display of track traces with the motion patterns types directed (1), moderate (2) and chaotic (3). The dots represent the coordinates of a track per video frame.

Thus, the velocity is calculated between each 2nd respectively 10th coordinate while skipping the coordinates in between. This definition of velocity is more robust against back and forth movements of subviral particles. The consideration of the distributions of the parameters in dependence of the manual class division show that the assignment by one single parameter is not sufficient and it requires the combination of more information. Principal component analysis (PCA) [8] was used for this purpose. In advance, the parameters values x were scaled that the mean value $\bar{x} = 0$ and the variance $\delta^2 = 1$. To classify new tracks, a filter was constructed using the scalar product of the parameter components and the parameter values of the new track. Model building for classification was performed by a support vector machine (SVM) [9] with linear kernel function under input of the training data. This model could then be used to predict the new track under input of the filter result. This model could then be used to classify the new track based on the filter result. Programs were written in Python 3.7.

Figure 2: Scatter plot of the second principal component (PC) vs. the first principal component (PC) with the support vectors and the decision functions shown as dashed lines resulting from the SVM. Measurements from the tracks shown in Fig. 1 are marked with 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

III. Results and discussion

The results obtained with the algorithm for the test data are presented as scatter plot that maps the second principal component (PC) versus the first PC (Fig. 2). The manually classified training data and the algorithmically reassigned track can also be seen in Figure 2. Additionally, resulting from the SVM, the support vectors are denoted by circles and the decision functions are shown as dashed lines. Clearly visible is the separation of the tracks into the three conjectured classes: directed, moderate, and chaotic. While the distribution of the directed tracks is almost linear, the chaotic tracks are arranged radially. The moderate tracks apparently represent a mixture of both arrangements. Individual parameters could not provide such a separation of the classes before the application of PCA. The SVM model creates a strict separation of classes based on a linear kernel function. In further steps, the radial base function SVM approach could also be used. The results show that the presented method is an effective way to classify subviral particle tracks. However, with the small training

data set, the possibility of randomness exists and should be further extended before making an informed conclusion. Thus, this graph should be considered as further evidence. In addition, the training data set relies on human assignment of classes, which means that errors can never be ruled out. Only when verified by several experts can the potential for errors be considered vanishingly small. Furthermore, the algorithm allows the assignment of new tracks to the respective class. First tests run with single tracks under consideration of the track traces are promising. The human mind assigns the tracks shown in Figure 1 to the same classes as the algorithm in Figure 2. However, this still has to be quantified on the basis of a sufficiently large training and test data set in cooperation with more virologic experts.

IV. Conclusions

This work shows that the tracks of subviral particles can indeed be classified by a machine learning approach as directed, moderate, and chaotic. Likewise, the algorithm allows the classification of new unassigned tracks. In the near future, the pool of underlying data needs to be expanded to increase reliability on the one hand and to test it on the other. This work forms another cornerstone for the future and reveals a lot of potential in this topic. For example, changes in track traces of subviral particles could be reassigned and visualized after the addition of pharmaceuticals without much effort.

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